

Audio file

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Transcript

Speaker 1

Hello, thank you so much for taking the time to participate in this research. My name is Anna Makanwizir and I'm pursuing a master's in software engineering and technology. And I'm conducting research for my master's thesis to investigate how developers in Medina perceive vulnerabilities in the open source experiences they use in their projects. This is given the background of the rising supply chain attacks that is happening through dependencies people are using in their project. And my research focuses on frameworks, Django, Next.js, Springboot, Daravail, and Ruben Rail. And just a few ethical considerations. Participation in this research is entirely voluntary and you can withdraw from the EW at any time. will not retain any personal data or identifiable information, and your name, e-mail address room, or any identifiable details will not be published or associated with anyone. You can skip any questions you're not comfortable answering, and your responses will remain anonymous and will not be linked to the project you represent. The interviews will be recorded and kept for the duration of the study to allow the supervisor to verify the authenticity of the reported data. after which they will be deleted. Yep. So we'll start maybe, could you please introduce yourself and then tell us which web framework you're using. If you are a developer in that framework that is, you're just using it for, are you a contributor or a median of the framework? If you are not maintain our computer of the framework. Maybe you can tell us also what you're working on as well as your role and the experience level of experience you have with the framework as well as your level of experience within the software development industry. Just for us to know your background.

Speaker 2

Hello, I'm Tilu, a software developer. I've been developing for close to 8 years now. And my main focus mainly Laravel and JavaScript. I've done a little bit of Ruby on Rails. I would consider on Ruby on Rails a beginner. I'm still grasping the concept of how the frameworks works and everything. But with Laravel and NPM, I am more first in those two. Currently, I'm not contributing to any open source to to anything to do with open source. I've mainly

been developing software for clients and projects. That's what I've mainly. That's what my main focus is on.

Speaker 1

Okay, and my research is mostly focused on security. So maybe for a start, I want to know how security issues handled in the projects that you work on. You said you're working on kind projects.

Speaker 2

So I think one of the major, I think one of the issues that that contains security that I mainly try to avoid is maybe having like client credentials being leaked, especially in the code base by using .env or environment file variables. In that way, I don't, when I commit my stuff to GitHub with times, if it's open source or anything, it won't have, if it's, if it's by open source, I mean something that everyone can see. It's not logged only to my account. I try to make sure that the environment variables are not exposed to everyone. And I think with me, maybe a little bit of background. The reason why I've sort of like stayed with mainly JavaScript and maybe mainly Laravel when it comes to maybe the issue that we have of supply chain attacks and inducing dependencies, I try to stick to division or look to a current vision that I'm working with at that time. And when it comes to maybe time to upgrading and mainly most of the time I I mainly depend on the GitHub alerts that are sent to me, but there's a particular package that we're using on a certain project. It needs to be moved maybe to another version, as in maybe due to a security alert or something that has been found. And what I've tried to also or what I've maybe like picked up in the last few days is When I upgrade to a package, I tend to get maybe a package that is at least seven days old or something that a package has been released maybe a few minutes ago and then I start using that. I need something that maybe has got like a week so that maybe like I think the last attack that happened with Axios on that one, I think I found I found that, in fact, I came across that issue on Twitter so early, so early in the morning and I just had to go through the projects, the ones that I had to make sure that maybe if I had installed any dependencies, it's not the affected vision. And also what I've picked up is maybe just trying to get maybe a vision that is at least one week old and also try to look versions of my dependence to a specific version that I know is not affected.

Speaker 1

Okay. So in other words, you are using Github dependable or get up advisors to get security issues to do with your project.

Speaker 2

Yes, yep, yes.

Speaker 1

Okay. you mentioned waiting one week, one week to update a dependency. You update that has been.

Speaker 2

Published for more than one week, because that at least gives me that at least gives me maybe like a little. I know that there are guys that say a package has been released and they just start scanning through like what happened with the last Axios issue. Once someone found an issue, they started reporting it. But within days, the issue had been resolved. So at least it gives me, I'm not saying that it's specific, but for me, I thought that maybe at least get a package whose age is at least one week old being, it being the latest that might actually help.

Speaker 1

Thank you. And how conscious are you of the dangers that vulnerable dependencies present to your project?

Speaker 2

I am very much aware. I tend to like, for example, I think within Laravel, we use like a lot of dependencies code that has been written by others. Maybe I need maybe to export HTML to to a PDF file, I might need to get a package. At times I have to Google and search when was it last updated. I tend to go to maybe stuff that I know they are being maintained rather than maybe something that was maybe last maintained 10 years ago. And with 10 years ago, a lot of changes have happened to software, their updates, their stuff, their vulnerabilities that would have been fixed. So it's mainly Yeah, I think, yeah, I think if that could maybe answer that question. If not, maybe I can rephrase it a bit better.

Speaker 1

Okay, I'll I was. It just answered the question. But I was going to offer a follow up question.

Speaker 2

Yeah.

Speaker 1

Is to what criteria do you use to choose what dependence you're going to include in your project? You can't get it on that.

Speaker 2

Okay, yeah. So that depends maybe with what I'm working on. and maybe with what I've been used to. For example, I know that when it comes to maybe to dealing with dates and everything. If I'm not a few, I just use carbon because I know that that package it's safe, it's secure. So it's it's just a mixture of both experience And also, what am I dealing with in that moment? And if there's a new package that I need to use, I still need to go down and maybe do a little bit of research. It's not like just saying composer installed this, and then it just gets onto my machine and I say, ah, everything is working.

Speaker 1

And how are you of supply chain attacks in their effects on projects?

Speaker 2

Yeah, so I think- Okay, yeah. So I think with supply chain, I think my knowledge, it has been like grown a bit in the last in the past few weeks. Due to the number of these attacks that are happening, it's tough that happens with you not knowing I just get a dependent and I think with the last one that happened, it would maybe like erase itself in the system once it has got what it needed into the system. So I think my knowledge is now a bit better. And now I need to be careful of what I am installing because it's not only about the client's project as well, it's also about the stuff that's on my machine as well. And it just comes back to, I think the previous answer that I gave whereby I said, it now comes down to I have to research or I have to get a package that is at least one week old so that it gives me maybe like a little bit of, it calms me down a bit. to say, yeah, this one might be a little bit secure as other people have looked into it and yep.

Speaker 1

Okay. And what you've mentioned about locking versions of packages you're using in your projects, what influenced the decision to update to newer versions dependencies within your projects? Do you object to keep up with the main releases or You only update when there's maybe a vulnerability that has been reported.

Speaker 2

So mainly when there's a vulnerability in the project one or maybe if I'm updating, maybe it's a project that I'm working on, it needs to be updated to the next division. Maybe let's say I was working on a lot of your 10 and now I'm a lot of your 12 and there is a package that's broken and I need to update it. So when I update it, it might mean that there is other stuff. that I will need to also update so that the project can still work as expected. So there's a

number of things that depends, but with me mainly sticking to a lot of our times is I know that if I stick, if I work on my project, maybe it's on Laravel 10 today, as long as there is no, maybe like I have not done maybe like a major PHP update onto my system, I know that it's always going to run. So there's a number of issues But mainly it's it's it's it's driven by by 2 things. If there's a security list that I get, and I am moving, maybe updating, maybe from one Php version to another, or from moving from one letter of your version to to another.

Speaker 1

And you mentioned the checks that you do when you are including dependency in your project. But then, how do you take the maintenance of dependencies that you have in your project? Because one thing that opens in open source is you might include a dependent today and then the creators abandon it and it becomes unmaintained. So how do you know that the dependents you are still using are being maintained and they will have updates if they see vulnerability to be addressed?

Speaker 2

Yeah, so I think at times, At times, it always comes back to the GitHub depend upon most of the times. And also if a package is now not being maintained, that one is a tricky one because at times I might not get time maybe to trick because it's a package that's being used by another package, but that package is not something maybe that I'm looking at. maybe that's directly. So that one it now just depends on. If I if I get a lead to say that this one is not available, if maybe by chance I say, I'm working on something, then I remember that I used to use this. And then this is now not maybe working as I needed to work. Then I I update it.

Speaker 1

Okay. And how long usually does it take to update vulnerable dependency of project?

Speaker 2

That's one. It's it's now depends on what that's dependent maybe is actual affecting. It was at times it might meet maybe need to maybe like changing the whole structure of of the project. Because I think there was one project whereby I just needed to move from one page division to another and took me about a week because I had now to go in. and change, there are some variables that were no longer available. There were some constants that were no longer available. So it now just depends on how big is the project. Because at times, once more thing can actually break the whole project and you have to go back to the building blocks. And at times, it's plug and play. You just update, everything starts working. So it just depends.

Speaker 1

And how do you handle vulnerable dependencies that are no longer being maintained. Suppose you help them in your project is a vulnerability that has been reported, but the project we serve is no longer being maintained. So there is no hope of getting security updates for it.

Speaker 2

So I think on that one, I would just look for an alternative, an alternative that's secure and one that is not maybe really like that much different from the one that I was using. because if it's no longer available, then it means that the only solution that I've got is to look for an alternative to make sure that the project that I'm working on is is too secure, and I have to get another dependent that that that that is still being maintained. Okay.

Speaker 1

So is this So is this the same approach you would do with even Javascript dependencies that you use in your project? If you want to determine.

Speaker 2

Yeah, that's the same. That's the same script that I that I do. And the times it's it's just running maybe composer audit to make sure that I have to check for vulnerabilities within the project that I'm working on. That's also one thing that I use.

Speaker 1

All right thank you and you also use npm audit for JavaScript updates yes okay uh what other practices and tools do you have in place to stop supply chain attacks in your projects?

Speaker 2

On those ones, I'm still researching. Currently, I don't have none. It's new. It's something new that you've mentioned to me.

Speaker 1

So if any of your projects being exported to supply chain attacks, you mentioned the Axios suppression attack, did it affect your project or something that you just read about?

Speaker 2

It's something that I just came across and I had to go and look the vision of Axios that I had.

Speaker 1

Okay. And are there any challenges you face which probably hinder you in addressing vulnerable dependencies within your project?

Speaker 2

I know. I know challenges at all.

Speaker 1

Okay. And could you tell me what factors help you to address vulnerable dependencies within your project? What is this that helps you to address the vulnerable dependencies?

Speaker 2

So what helps me is I mainly depend on the Gita ballots. When something comes in, it means that I just have to move. If there is a better version, I have to move to a better version of that same dependence whereby the issues have been resolved. But still, if there are any other, maybe that I'm not getting, I just need to go back to composer audit to get the list of vulnerabilities within the projects that I'm working on. Then I just have to change to a better vision or look for an alternative that still suits the issue that I was trying to resolve.

Speaker 1

My last question for you is, do you have any recommendations for dependent management? regards to supply chain attacks.

Speaker 2

On that one, I think most of the times maybe it's just down to maybe to the developer, I think, to the developers because it's not only, it's being about maybe being vigilant of maybe like social engineering, like what's happened to the maintain of access, and how they could maybe attacked on their account, so that it resulted in the supply chain. So there are number of things. It's just being aware of maybe social engineering and being aware of. Maybe when you when you develop some, when you, when, when there's a dependence that you need At times, maybe 75% of the code has been written by humans, 25% by AI or vice versa. There is still going to be mistakes that are going to be made. We still need maybe to be vigilant and to exactly know what are you getting so that you get exactly what you need.

Speaker 1

Thank you so much for taking your time to participate in this interview. I really appreciate it.

Speaker 2

You're welcome.